

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN RURAL DEVELOPMENT: STRENGTHENING COMMUNITY PARTICIPATION FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH

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ABSTRACT

Rural development is one of the important aspects in realizing equitable development and improving community welfare. However, various challenges such as limited resources, low community participation, and weak coordination between stakeholders are still obstacles to the implementation of sustainable village development. Therefore, a governance approach is needed that is able to integrate various development actors effectively. This study aims to analyze the role of collaborative governance in strengthening community participation to support sustainable rural growth. The research uses a literature review method with a qualitative approach through the analysis of various scientific articles, books, and academic documents relevant to the themes of collaborative governance, community participation, and rural development. The results of the study show that collaborative governance plays an important role in increasing community involvement in the planning, implementation, and evaluation

process of village development. The success of collaboration is influenced by facilitative leadership, inter-stakeholder trust, effective communication, clear institutional design, and shared commitment to achieving development goals. On the other hand, limited human resource capacity, low digital literacy, and weak coordination are factors that hinder the implementation of collaboration. This study concludes that collaborative governance can be an effective strategy to strengthen community participation and promote inclusive, self-reliant, and sustainable rural development.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance, Community Participation, Rural Development, Collaborative Governance, Sustainable Growth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Villages have a strategic role in national development because they become living spaces for most Indonesian people as well as a center of economic, social, and cultural activities. Since the enactment of Law Number 6 of 2014 concerning Villages, the government has given greater authority to villages to regulate and manage development in accordance with their needs, potentials, and local characteristics. The policy aims to improve community welfare, strengthen village independence, and encourage community participation in the development process.

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Village development commitments are also strengthened through the implementation of *the Village's Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) which are oriented towards poverty alleviation, improving the quality of life of the community, equitable economic growth, and environmental conservation. In the Indonesian context, the success of village development is measured through the Building Village Index (IDM) which includes the dimensions of social resilience, economic resilience, and environmental resilience. Successful village development is not only marked by an increase in infrastructure, but also by increasing community capacity and village independence in managing its resources (Nuryanto et al., 2021).

Despite the various policies that have been implemented, rural development still faces various challenges. Many villages are still in the developing category and have not been able to achieve the status of independent villages. These conditions are influenced by limited facilities and infrastructure, low levels of community income, not optimal utilization of local potential, and low community participation in the development process (Nuryanto et al., 2021). In addition, the development of village development also faces challenges in the form of gaps between regions, limited innovation, low human resource capacity, and suboptimal synergy between development actors (Alkadafi et al., 2025).

These various problems show that rural development cannot rely solely on the role of the government as a single actor. The concept of *governance* emphasizes a shift from a centralistic governance pattern towards the involvement of various actors, namely the government, the private sector, and the community in the process of conducting public affairs (Ulum & Ngindana, 2017 in Nuryanto et al., 2021). The involvement of these various actors is important because the complexity of village development problems requires resources, knowledge, and capacity that cannot be fulfilled by one party alone.

In this context, the concept of **Collaborative Governance** is one of the relevant approaches to be applied in rural development. Ansell and Gash (2008) define *Collaborative Governance* as a governance arrangement that involves government agencies and non-government stakeholders in a decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and aims to solve public problems together. Through a collaborative approach, governments, communities, the private sector, academics, and civil society organizations can build cooperation to achieve more effective and sustainable development goals.

The success of collaborative governance is greatly influenced by the level of community participation. Community participation is not only interpreted as involvement in the implementation of development activities, but also includes involvement in the process of planning, decision-making, implementation, and evaluation of development programs. Arnstein (1969) explained that quality participation occurs when people have a real opportunity to influence decisions related to their interests. Therefore, community participation is an important factor in realizing inclusive and sustainable development.

The importance of community participation in village development is also emphasized by Nuryanto et al. (2021) who stated that strengthening community participation is the main factor in supporting village renewal and development. A high level of community involvement will encourage the formation of village independence because the community is not only the beneficiary of development, but also the main actor in determining the direction of village development. In addition, village development is basically a process to strengthen *community self-reliance* through the ability of the community to identify problems, determine solutions, and manage their resources independently (Usman, 2015 in Nuryanto et al., 2021).

Various previous studies have discussed the implementation of collaborative governance in village development and efforts to realize independent villages. However, most of the research still focuses on specific case studies and deals more with the process of collaboration between

actors in a partial way. Studies that specifically integrate the relationship between collaborative governance, community participation, and sustainable growth in the context of rural development are still relatively limited. Therefore, a study that is able to synthesize various research findings is needed to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the role of collaborative governance in strengthening community participation to support sustainable rural growth.

Based on this background, this study aims to analyze the role of collaborative governance in strengthening community participation and its contribution to sustainable growth in rural areas. Through a *literature review* approach, this study is expected to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that support the success of collaborative governance and its implications for rural development in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Collaborative Governance

Collaborative governance is an approach that emphasizes the involvement of various stakeholders in the decision-making process and resolution of public issues. According to Ansell and Gash (2008), *Collaborative Governance* is a governance arrangement that involves government agencies and non-government actors in a decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and aims to achieve common interests.

This approach developed in response to the complexity of public problems that cannot be solved by the government independently. In the context of rural development, collaborative governance allows for synergy between village governments, communities, the private sector, academia, and civil society organizations in planning and implementing development in a participatory manner (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Ansell and Gash (2008) explained that the success of collaborative governance is influenced by four main components, namely *starting conditions*, *facilitative leadership*, *institutional design*, and *collaborative process*. These four components are the foundation in building effective cooperation between development actors.

Table 1. Components of Collaborative Governance According to Ansell and Gash (2008)

Components	Description
Starting Conditions	Initial conditions that affect the formation of collaboration
Facilitative Leadership	Leadership that is able to facilitate cooperation between actors
Institutional Design	Rules and mechanisms that govern the collaboration process
Collaborative Process	Interaction, dialogue, and trust building between actors

Source: Adapted from *Collaborative Governance Components According to Ansell and Gash (2008)*, and processed by the author (2026).

In rural development, collaborative governance is important because it is able to integrate various resources, knowledge, and interests owned by stakeholders so that development goals can be achieved more effectively and sustainably (Alkadafi et al., 2025).

Community Participation in Rural Development

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Community participation is the active involvement of the community in the entire development process, starting from planning, implementation, utilization of results, to evaluation of development programs. Participation is one of the important indicators of development success because the community not only plays a role as a beneficiary, but also as a development actor.

Arnstein (1969) explained that community participation can be measured through eight levels known as *the Ladder of Citizen Participation*. This model shows that the quality of participation is determined by the level of community influence in the decision-making process.

Table 2. Arnstein's Ladder of Participation (1969)

Levels	Categories
Citizen Control	Full participation
Delegated Power	Delegated power
Partnership	Partnerships
Plating	Consultative
Consultation	Consultation
Informing	Providing information
Therapy	Pseudo-participation
Handling	Non-participatory

Source: Adapted from Arnstein's Participation Ladder (1969), and processed by the author (2026).

In rural development, community participation has an important role in increasing the effectiveness of development programs. People who are actively involved tend to have a higher *sense of ownership* of the programs that are carried out so that sustainable development is easier to realize (Nuryanto et al., 2021).

Nuryanto et al. (2021) explained that the success of village development is greatly influenced by the level of community participation. Community involvement in the development process is able to encourage the formation of village independence and increase the capacity of the community to manage their resources.

Sustainable Rural Development

Sustainable rural development is a development process that aims to improve the welfare of village communities while still paying attention to economic, social, and environmental aspects. This approach is in line with the concept of *Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs) which emphasizes the importance of inclusive and sustainable development.

In the Indonesian context, sustainable development at the village level is realized through the Village SDGs which include various development goals, such as poverty alleviation, improving the quality of education, public health, village economic growth, and environmental conservation.

Alkadafi et al. (2025) explained that sustainable village development requires synergy between the government and the community in utilizing local resources effectively. Collaboration between actors is an important factor in increasing village capacity to achieve sustainable development goals.

In addition, Nuryanto et al. (2021) emphasized that village development is not only oriented towards economic growth, but also on improving the quality of life of the community, strengthening village institutions, and sustainable resource management.

Frame of Mind

This research departs from the assumption that the success of rural development is not only determined by the capacity of the village government, but also by the involvement of various stakeholders in the development process. Collaborative governance is a mechanism that is able to strengthen community participation so as to encourage the realization of sustainable rural growth.

Figure 1. Frame of Mind

Source: Adapted from Ansell & Gash (2008), Arnstein (1969), and Processed by the author (2026).

This frame of thinking shows that collaborative governance plays a role as a factor that encourages increased community participation. Strong participation will support the implementation of more effective, inclusive, and sustainable rural development. supporting the empowerment of rural MSMEs in a sustainable manner.

3. METHODS

This study uses a **literature review** method with a qualitative approach to analyze various literature related to collaborative *governance*, community participation, and sustainable rural development. This method was chosen because it is able to provide a comprehensive understanding of the concepts, research findings, and developments of studies relevant to the research topic.

The data used are secondary data obtained from various scientific sources, such as journal articles, books, and academic documents that discuss collaborative governance in rural development. Literature was collected through searching academic databases, including Google Scholar, Garuda, Scopus, and other scientific sources using the keywords *Collaborative Governance*, *Community Participation*, *Rural Development*, *Village Development*, and *Sustainable Development*.

The literature used was selected based on its relevance to the research focus, namely the relationship between collaborative governance, community participation, and sustainable growth in rural areas. Prioritized sources are scientific articles that have gone through a *peer review* process and are directly related to village development and collaborative governance.

Data analysis was carried out using qualitative descriptive analysis techniques. The analysis stages include identification of literature, grouping of themes, interpretation of findings, and synthesis of various relevant research results. The analysis focuses on the role of collaborative governance in strengthening community participation, the factors that support and hinder collaboration, and its contribution to sustainable rural development.

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The research analysis framework refers to the *Collaborative Governance* model proposed by Ansell and Gash (2008), which consists of *starting conditions*, *facilitative leadership*, *institutional design*, and *collaborative process*. The framework is used to understand how the process of collaboration between actors can increase community participation and support the achievement of sustainable rural development goals.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Role of Collaborative Governance in Rural Development

The results of the literature review show that collaborative governance is becoming an increasingly important approach in rural development. The complexity of village problems, ranging from poverty, limited institutional capacity, development gaps, to low community participation, cannot be solved by the village government alone. Therefore, the involvement of various actors such as government, society, the private sector, academia, and the media is needed to achieve sustainable development goals (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Research by Alkadafi et al. (2025) shows that effective village development requires integration between government approaches and community participation through collaborative governance models. The model is able to bridge various interests while strengthening the legitimacy, transparency, and effectiveness of village development. In addition, collaboration allows for the exchange of resources, information, and knowledge needed to solve various village development problems (Alkadafi et al., 2025).

In the context of sustainable village development, collaborative governance not only serves as a coordination mechanism, but also as a means to strengthen local capacity. Aguswan et al. (2025) explained that sustainable village development planning requires the involvement of the government, the private sector, civil society, universities, and the mass media in development planning forums such as Development Planning Deliberations (Musrenbang). The involvement of these various actors allows for development that is more responsive to the needs of the community and the local conditions of the village.

Table 3. The Role of Actors in Collaborative Governance of Rural Development

Actors	Main Role
Government	Regulators, facilitators, and development coordinators
Society	Development participants and beneficiaries
Private	Investment and economic support providers
Academics	Research, innovation, and mentoring providers
Media	Information dissemination and social control

Source: Processed by the Author (2026).

Collaborative Governance and Strengthening Community Participation

Community participation is an important element in the success of rural development. The literature shows that communities involved in the development process tend to have a higher level of concern and responsibility for the sustainability of the programs implemented. Such participation is not only limited to the implementation of activities, but also includes the process of planning, decision-making, supervision, and evaluation of development (Arnstein, 1969).

Nuryanto et al. (2021) emphasized that the level of community participation is a factor that greatly determines the success of village development. The higher the community involvement, the greater the opportunity to create development that is in accordance with local needs and able to increase village independence.

Collaborative governance provides a wider space for communities to be involved in the development process. Through the mechanism of dialogue, deliberation, and joint decision-making, the community is no longer placed as an object of development, but as a subject who has the right to determine the direction of village development. This condition is in line with the concept of citizen power put forward by Arnstein (1969), which is when society has a real influence in the decision-making process.

Research by Aguswan et al. (2025) shows that the Musrenbang forum is an important instrument in realizing community participation because it allows various community groups to convey development needs and aspirations directly. Participatory planning will result in more effective, targeted, and sustainable programs.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors of Collaborative Governance

The results of the literature synthesis show that the success of collaborative governance is influenced by several supporting factors. Ansell and Gash (2008) identified four main elements that determine the success of collaboration, namely starting conditions, institutional design, facilitative leadership, and collaborative process. Aguswan et al. (2025) also emphasized that the commitment of all parties to actively participate is the key to the success of sustainable village development.

Table 4. Supporting Factors for Collaborative Governance

Factors	Explanation
Facilitative Leadership	Encourage coordination and cooperation between actors
Trust	Strengthen commitment and willingness to collaborate
Communication	Facilitate information exchange
Stakeholder Participation	Increase development resources and capacity
Institutional Design	Provide collaboration rules and mechanisms

Source: Processed Author (2026).

On the other hand, various studies have also found a number of obstacles in the implementation of collaborative governance. These obstacles include limited human resource capacity, low digital literacy, inequality in development between regions, weak coordination, and low participation of certain groups in the development process (Jaiz et al., 2025). Serang Regency, for example, still faces the problem of low digital literacy of the community, limited internet access, and low involvement of women in the village development process.

Table 5. Factors That Hinder Collaborative Governance

Factors	Impact
Human Resources Limitations	Lowering the effectiveness of the program
Low Digital Literacy	Hindering development innovation
Conflict of Interest	Complicating joint decision-making
Regional Inequality	Creating development gaps
Low Participation	Reducing the legitimacy of development

Source: Processed Author (2026).

The Contribution of Collaborative Governance to Sustainable Growth

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The literature shows that collaborative governance has a significant contribution to the achievement of sustainable rural development. Collaboration allows various actors to integrate their resources and capacities so that development is not only oriented towards economic growth, but also on improving social welfare and environmental conservation.

Research by Jaiz et al. (2025) shows that *Pentahelix-based* collaboration is able to increase the Developing Village Index (IDM) by 18.71%, reduce the village poverty rate by 4.08%, and strengthen the circular economy of village communities. The findings show that synergy between government, academia, the private sector, the community, and the media can have a real impact on sustainable rural development.

In addition, collaborative governance also contributes to improving the quality of village development planning. Through the involvement of various actors in the Musrenbang process, development becomes more participatory and in accordance with the needs of the community. Aguswan et al. (2025) emphasized that the success of sustainable village development is highly determined by the ability of stakeholders to build sustainable commitment and cooperation.

Table 6. The Impact of Collaborative Governance on Rural Development

Aspects	Impact
Economy	Increased income and poverty reduction
Social	Increase community participation and capacity
Institutional	Strengthening village governance
Environment	Supporting sustainable development
Technology	Encouraging innovation and village digitalization

Source: Processed Author (2026)

Synthesis of Study Results

Based on all the literature analyzed, it can be understood that collaborative governance is an effective approach in supporting sustainable rural development. The success of collaboration is strongly influenced by facilitative leadership, inter-stakeholder trust, clear institutional design, and active community participation. On the other hand, limited human resources, low digital literacy, and weak coordination are factors that can hinder the success of collaboration. The research findings also show that community participation is a key bridge between collaborative governance and sustainable growth. The higher the level of community participation in the development process, the greater the opportunity for the creation of inclusive, independent, and sustainable village development. Therefore, strengthening collaborative governance needs to be directed at increasing community capacity, strengthening village institutions, and building sustainable partnerships between village development actors.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the literature review, it can be concluded that collaborative *governance* has an important role in supporting sustainable rural development. This approach allows for synergy between the government, the community, the private sector, academics, and the media in the process of planning, implementing, and evaluating village development. Collaboration between actors is important because the complexity of rural development problems cannot be solved by one party independently (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

The results of the study show that community participation is a key element in the success of collaborative governance. Community involvement in the development process is able to increase the effectiveness of the program, strengthen the sense of ownership of development results, and encourage the creation of village independence. The higher the level of community participation, the greater the chance of realizing development in accordance with the local needs and potential of the village (Arnstein, 1969; Nuryanto et al., 2021).

The study also found that the success of collaborative governance is influenced by several supporting factors, including facilitative leadership, inter-stakeholder trust, effective communication, clear institutional design, and shared commitment to achieving development goals. On the other hand, limited human resources, low digital literacy, weak coordination, and inequality of capacity between regions are factors that can hinder the implementation of collaboration in rural development (Jaiz et al., 2025; Aguswan et al., 2025).

Overall, collaborative governance has been proven to contribute to sustainable rural growth through increased community participation, strengthening village institutional capacity, developing local economies, and improving the quality of development planning. Therefore, collaborative governance can be seen as one of the relevant approaches in supporting the achievement of inclusive, independent, and sustainable rural development.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the study, the village government needs to strengthen collaboration mechanisms with various stakeholders through participatory forums that are able to accommodate the aspirations of the community more broadly. Strengthening the capacity of village officials and the community also needs to be done to improve the quality of participation in the development process. In addition, efforts are needed to strengthen partnerships between village governments, the private sector, universities, community organizations, and the media to support innovation and sustainability of village development. An integrated collaborative approach is expected to increase the effectiveness of development programs and accelerate the achievement of sustainable development goals at the village level.

For further research, it is recommended to conduct empirical studies in specific villages to directly test the relationship between collaborative governance, community participation, and sustainable growth. Field research will provide a more in-depth picture of collaborative practices as well as the factors that influence their success in the context of rural development.

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